

One health approach to antimicrobial resistance: Integrating human, animal, and environmental perspectives

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ABSTRACT

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a critical global health threat that transcends human, animal, and environmental sectors, necessitating a One Health approach. AMR arises from the misuse and overuse of antimicrobial agents in clinical, veterinary, and environmental settings, resulting in treatment failures and heightened mortality rates. By 2050, AMR is projected to cause 10 million deaths annually and incur a global economic loss of 1 trillion USD. Low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) are expected to bear a significant burden, potentially accounting for 5 million of these deaths and facing substantial economic challenges due to limited access to healthcare resources and second-line antibiotics. In human health, excessive antibiotic prescriptions and hospital-acquired infections have been identified as major drivers of resistance, exacerbated by poor infection control, and the lack of rapid diagnostic tools. Similarly, in veterinary medicine, the use of antimicrobials in livestock for disease prevention and growth promotion contributes significantly to AMR. Resistant bacteria from animals can transmit to humans through direct contact, the food chain, and environmental contamination. The environment further amplifies resistance through pharmaceutical waste, wastewater treatment inefficiencies, and the accumulation of resistant genes in ecosystems. Global efforts to address AMR include regulatory frameworks for prudent antimicrobial use in agriculture, human medicine, and waste management, alongside research into alternatives like phage therapy, immunotherapies, and improved diagnostics. Future solutions must focus on innovation, public engagement, and multi-sectoral collaboration to tackle the rising tide of resistance. The aim of this review is to explore the issue of AMR from a One Health perspective, highlighting the challenges faced by LMICs.

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Introduction

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) has emerged as one of the most pressing public health threats of the 21st century [1]. The phenomenon is characterized by the ability of microbes—bacteria, fungi, viruses, and parasites—to resist the effects of antimicrobial drugs, including antibiotics, antifungals, and antivirals, rendering treatments ineffective and leading to persistent infections, spread of disease, and higher mortality [2]. Addressing AMR requires a holistic, multisectoral approach, encapsulated by the One Health paradigm, which recognizes that

the health of humans, animals, and ecosystems is intricately connected [3]. The rapid rise of resistant infections across all three domains highlights the urgent need for a coordinated global response to address antimicrobial use, transmission pathways, and the environmental consequences of pharmaceutical contaminants [4].

Many LMICs struggle with inadequate healthcare infrastructure, leading to limited access to essential medical services, including antibiotics. This can result in the overuse or misuse of antibiotics, promoting the development of resistant bacteria [5]. Additionally, the availability of counterfeit or sub-

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standard drugs can further exacerbate the problem [6]. In LMICs, antibiotics are often prescribed indiscriminately, even for minor ailments or viral infections. This overuse contributes to the development of antibiotic resistance. Furthermore, the lack of proper infection control measures and inadequate sanitation practices facilitate the spread of resistant bacteria (Figure 1). Below graphically presents the concepts within this review.

Human Health and Antimicrobial Resistance

Over-Prescription and Misuse in Clinical Settings

In human health, the over-prescription of antibiotics is a significant driver of AMR. It is estimated that 30%–50% of antibiotic prescriptions in clinical settings are unnecessary or inappropriate [7]. Patients often pressure healthcare providers for antibiotics for viral infections such as the common

cold, which do not respond to antibiotics, leading to the overuse of broad-spectrum agents. Lack of education among patients regarding antibiotic use also contributes to AMR in Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs) [8]. This indiscriminate use allows bacteria to adapt and evolve resistance mechanisms, which are often carried on mobile genetic elements such as plasmids that can be transferred horizontally between bacterial species [9].

Additionally, the healthcare environment, particularly hospitals, contributes to the spread of resistant organisms. Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs) caused by multi-drug-resistant organisms (MDROs) such as *Clostridium difficile*, *Methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), and *Carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae* (CRE) are among the most prevalent [10]. These pathogens are particularly problematic in intensive care units (ICUs), where immunocompromised patients are often treated with high doses of antibiotics [11].

Figure 1. Graphical presentation of One Health aspects and AMR.

Global Burden of AMR in Human Health

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), AMR contributes to nearly 700,000 deaths annually, with projections suggesting this number could rise to 10 million by 2050 if current trends continue [12]. The economic toll of AMR is also significant, with estimates suggesting that it could reduce global Gross Domestic Product (GDP) by 2%–3.5% by 2050 [13,14]. AMR exacerbates global inequalities, disproportionately affecting LMICs where access to second-line antibiotics and diagnostic tools is limited [15].

The above Table 1 highlights the projected global and regional impacts of AMR by 2050. Globally, AMR could result in 10 million deaths annually and an economic loss of 1 trillion USD. The United States may face 2.4 million deaths and a 128 billion USD economic impact, while Europe could see 1.3 million deaths and a 100 billion USD loss. LMICs are projected to be heavily affected, with 5 million deaths and the same economic impact as the global projection (1 trillion USD).

Interventions in Human Healthcare

Addressing AMR in human health requires the implementation of robust antimicrobial stewardship programs (ASPs) that promote the rational use of antibiotics. These programs focus on optimizing antibiotic selection, dosing, route of administration, and duration of therapy to minimize resistance selection pressure [18]. The importance of infection prevention and control (IPC) measures, including hand hygiene, environmental cleaning, and isolation protocols for MDRO carriers, cannot be overstated [19]. Furthermore, innovation in diagnostic tools is crucial to reduce the unnecessary use of antibiotics by enabling rapid identification of bacterial versus viral infections [20].

Additionally, Addressing ASPs in LMICs is crucial for enhancing the global fight against AMR. ASPs in these regions face unique challenges such as limited healthcare infrastructure, inadequate funding, and

a lack of trained healthcare professionals. A comprehensive approach that includes strengthening public awareness campaigns is vital, as these initiatives can educate communities on the importance of appropriate antimicrobial use and adherence to prescribed treatments. For instance, a study by Muddenda et al. highlights gaps in healthcare workers' knowledge, awareness, and practices concerning antimicrobial use, resistance, and stewardship in Zambia, emphasizing the need for tailored training programs and public health campaigns to mitigate AMR effectively. By expanding ASPs and awareness efforts in LMICs, global health strategies can become more inclusive and impactful, bridging disparities, and ensuring sustainable healthcare practices worldwide [21].

Veterinary Medicine and Antimicrobial Resistance in Animals

Antimicrobial Use in Livestock and Aquaculture

The use of antimicrobials in veterinary medicine, particularly in livestock production, is a major contributor to the development of AMR. In many parts of the world, antibiotics are routinely used not only to treat infections in animals but also as growth promoters and prophylactic agents. The practice of using antibiotics as feed additives to promote growth in livestock has been identified as a key factor in the rise of resistant bacteria, particularly in food animals such as chickens, pigs, and cattle [22].

The spread of resistant bacteria from animals to humans occurs through several pathways, including direct contact with livestock, the consumption of contaminated meat, and environmental transmission via manure and agricultural runoff. Studies have shown that antibiotic-resistant bacteria, including *Escherichia coli* and *Campylobacter*, can be transmitted from animals to humans through the food chain, leading to severe infections that are difficult to treat [23]. Table 2 below reveals significant antibiotic re-

Table 1. Projected mortality and economic impacts of antimicrobial resistance (AMR).

Region/Country	Projected mortality (deaths/year)	Economic impact (USD billions)	Reference
Global	10 million (by 2050)	1 trillion (by 2050)	[16]
United States	2.4 million (by 2050)	128 billion (by 2050)	[16]}
Europe	1.3 million (by 2050)	100 billion (by 2050)	[17]
Low- and middle-income countries	5 million (by 2050)	1 trillion (by 2050)	[16]

Table 2. Prevalence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria in livestock in LMICs from recent studies.

Study/Sourvce (year)	Region/Country	Antibiotic-resistant bacteria identified	Prevalence/Impact
Magnusson et al. (2021) [24]	Sub-Saharan Africa	Salmonella, Escherichia coli	Up to 60% resistance to tetracycline and sulfonamides in poultry samples
Hedma et al. (2020) [25]	Southeast Asia	Staphylococcus aureus, Campylobacter	Over 55% of poultry showed resistance to multiple antibiotics, including ciprofloxacin
Haque et al. (2022) [26]	South Asia (Bangladesh, India)	Escherichia coli	47% resistance rate in cattle farms, impacting food safety and public health

sistance in livestock across LMICs, with up to 60% of poultry in Sub-Saharan Africa resistant, over 55% in Southeast Asia, and 47% in South Asia.

Regulatory Frameworks and Global Efforts

Some countries, including those in the European Union, have banned the use of antibiotics as growth promoters. However, enforcement remains inconsistent globally, particularly in LMICs, where regulation of veterinary practices is weak [27]. The World Organization for Animal Health (WOAH) has called for the prudent use of antimicrobials in veterinary medicine, emphasizing the need for veterinary oversight, prescription requirements, and bans on the use of antibiotics for growth promotion [28–30].

Recent efforts in LMICs show promising advancements in regulating veterinary antibiotic use. For example, Kenya has implemented stricter measures, including mandatory veterinary prescriptions for antibiotic sales, improving regulatory compliance and reducing misuse. Similarly, Bangladesh is promoting alternative livestock management practices, like enhanced biosecurity and vaccination programs, to minimize the need for antibiotics. These efforts underscore the significance of tailored regulations and strategies in LMICs, strengthening the One Health approach to tackling antimicrobial resistance globally [15].

Alternatives to Antibiotics in Veterinary Medicine

To reduce the reliance on antibiotics in animal husbandry, alternative approaches to disease prevention and growth promotion are being explored. These include the use of probiotics, prebiotics, and phytogenic compounds, as well as vaccines to prevent bacterial infections in livestock [31]. Improvements in animal husbandry practices, including better biosecurity, hygiene, and vaccination proto-

cols, are also essential to reduce the need for antibiotics in food animal production [32].

The Role of the Environment in Antimicrobial Resistance

Environmental Reservoirs of AMR

The environment plays a crucial role in the emergence and dissemination of antimicrobial resistance. Pharmaceuticals, including antibiotics, are released into the environment through various pathways, including human and animal waste, pharmaceutical manufacturing, and the improper disposal of unused medications. These contaminants enter soil, water, and air, creating reservoirs of resistant bacteria and resistance genes in environmental ecosystems [33–35].

Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) have been identified as key points of AMR dissemination. While these facilities are designed to remove contaminants from water, they often fail to completely eliminate antibiotics and resistant bacteria [36]. As a result, WWTPs can serve as hot spots for the horizontal gene transfer of resistance genes between bacteria, which can then spread through surface water, groundwater, and soil. Antibiotic residues in the environment can also exert selective pressure on microbial communities, promoting the persistence and proliferation of resistant strains [37].

Zhuang et al. emphasize that WWTPs are significant sources of antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) due to their inefficiency in fully removing antibiotic residues. Successful mitigation strategies include optimizing treatment processes like advanced oxidation and biofiltration to reduce ARGs more effectively [33]. However, challenges remain in regulating pharmaceutical companies' discharges, especially in LMICs, where regulations are often underdeveloped or poorly enforced. Strengthen-

ing policies and implementing effective treatment methods are critical to minimizing environmental contributions to antimicrobial resistance.

AMR in Aquatic Ecosystems

Aquatic environments are particularly vulnerable to AMR contamination due to the release of pharmaceutical residues from human and veterinary sources. Antibiotics and resistant bacteria have been detected in rivers, lakes, and oceans, where they can be taken up by aquatic organisms, further amplifying the spread of resistance [38]. For example, studies have documented the presence of resistant bacteria in fish and shellfish, raising concerns about the potential for AMR transmission through seafood consumption [39].

Strategies for Environmental AMR Control

Addressing AMR in the environment requires a multisectoral approach that includes improved wastewater management, stricter regulations on pharmaceutical manufacturing and disposal, and the development of new technologies to remove antibiotics from water. Constructed wetlands, advanced oxidation processes, and membrane filtration systems have shown promise in reducing the levels of antibiotics and resistant bacteria in wastewater [40,41]. Additionally, reducing the use of antibiotics in agriculture and veterinary medicine is essential to prevent further contamination of the environment with resistant organisms [40].

One Health and Global Policy Initiatives

The Role of International Organizations

The One Health approach to AMR has been endorsed by several international organizations, including the WHO, the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), and the World Organization for Animal Health (WOAH). These organizations have developed action plans to promote the responsible use of antimicrobials in human, animal, and environmental health and to strengthen surveillance systems for monitoring AMR [42,43]. The Global Action Plan on AMR, launched by the WHO in 2015, calls for coordinated action across sectors to reduce the incidence of infections, optimize the use of antimicrobials, and develop sustainable economic and investment strategies to address AMR [42].

National Action Plans and Regional Efforts

Many countries have developed national action plans (NAPs) to combat AMR, which align with the objectives of the Global Action Plan. These NAPs emphasize the need for multisectoral collaboration, surveillance, antimicrobial stewardship, and public awareness campaigns to reduce the spread of resistant infections [21,44,45]. However, the implementation of these plans varies widely across regions, with many LMICs facing significant challenges in terms of funding, infrastructure, and capacity-building [44,45]. For instance, in Bangladesh, a multisectoral collaboration involving the Ministry of Health, Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock, and environmental agencies has led to the development of an integrated surveillance system for antimicrobial use and resistance. This system tracks antibiotic usage patterns in both human and animal populations, enabling more targeted interventions and policy-making [46]. Another example is found in Kenya, where the Fleming Fund has supported the establishment of a national AMR surveillance program that connects human and veterinary laboratories. This collaborative effort has enhanced the country's capacity to detect and respond to resistant infections, demonstrating the effectiveness of the One Health approach in strengthening AMR control efforts in resource-limited settings [47].

The Role of Research and Innovation

Research and innovation are critical to addressing the AMR crisis. The development of new antibiotics, alternative therapies, and diagnostic tools is essential to reduce reliance on existing antimicrobials and to prevent the emergence of resistance. Phage therapy, which uses bacteriophages to target and kill specific bacterial pathogens, has shown promise as an alternative to antibiotics [48,49].

AMR Surveillance and Control in the MENA region

Hafez et al. provide insights into the challenges of AMR surveillance and control in the MENA region. The study highlights the widespread issue of non-prescription antibiotic sales in community pharmacies across 19 Arab countries, which significantly contributes to AMR. Despite existing regulations, enforcement remains inconsistent, leading to gaps in surveillance and policy implementation.

Strengthening pharmacist training and regulatory frameworks is essential to address these challenges and improve compliance with antimicrobial stewardship measures in the region [50].

Future Directions: Critical Challenges and Opportunities

Innovation in Diagnostics and Therapeutics

The ongoing threat of AMR calls for an urgent need to develop new antibiotics, alternative therapies, and advanced diagnostic tools. Despite advances in medicine, the pipeline for new antibiotics has slowed significantly, largely due to the high cost of research, stringent regulatory hurdles, and low profitability of these drugs compared to long-term therapies for chronic conditions [51,52]. However, recent innovations provide a glimmer of hope in combating AMR through alternative approaches such as phage therapy, immunotherapies, and novel diagnostic tools [53].

Phage Therapy

Phage therapy, which uses bacteriophages (viruses that infect bacteria) to specifically target and destroy bacterial cells, has re-emerged as a promising alternative to traditional antibiotics. Phage therapy offers advantages such as specificity for target bacteria and the ability to evolve alongside bacterial pathogens, reducing the likelihood of resistance [54,55]. Although phage therapy has shown success in preclinical studies and some compassionate use cases, it faces significant regulatory challenges in most countries. The lack of standardized production protocols, variable patient outcomes, and the complexities of phage-bacterial interactions have slowed clinical approval and widespread adoption [56]. Despite this, countries like Georgia and Russia have long used phage therapy in clinical practice, providing a model for its potential integration into global healthcare systems [57,58].

Ongoing research efforts aim to address these challenges. Phage cocktails, which use multiple phages to target various bacterial strains, are under investigation to overcome issues related to bacterial resistance. Several clinical trials are also underway to assess the efficacy of phage therapy against multidrug-resistant infections [59]. For instance, a 2020 study demonstrated phage therapy's ability to treat a drug-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* infection in a cystic fibrosis patient,

showcasing its potential as a complementary therapy to antibiotics [60].

Immunotherapies

Immunotherapy, which harnesses the body's immune system to fight infections, is another alternative being explored to combat AMR. One promising approach is the use of monoclonal antibodies to target specific bacterial toxins or surface proteins, effectively neutralizing pathogens without directly killing them. This strategy reduces selective pressure on bacteria, limiting the development of resistance [61]. For example, monoclonal antibodies against *C. difficile* toxins have been developed to prevent recurrent infections in patients treated with antibiotics. Clinical trials for antibody-based therapies targeting *S. aureus* and other resistant pathogens are currently ongoing, offering a novel avenue for AMR intervention [62].

Immunotherapies could be used as standalone treatments or in combination with traditional antibiotics to improve patient outcomes. However, their widespread use is hampered by high development costs, limited efficacy in some cases, and the complexity of immune responses in different patient populations. More research is needed to address these limitations and bring immunotherapies into routine clinical practice [63,64].

Diagnostic Tools

Rapid and accurate diagnostics are essential in the fight against AMR, as they enable healthcare providers to distinguish between bacterial and viral infections, thus preventing unnecessary antibiotic use. Currently, most diagnostic methods are either too slow (e.g., bacterial cultures) or lack specificity (e.g., broad-spectrum PCR assays). Recent innovations in point-of-care diagnostic tools, such as CRISPR-based technologies and next-generation sequencing, offer faster and more precise identification of pathogens and resistance genes [65].

For instance, CRISPR-Cas systems have been adapted for diagnostic purposes, allowing for rapid and sensitive detection of bacterial infections and resistance markers. The SHERLOCK and DETECTR platforms, which utilize CRISPR technology, have demonstrated the potential to identify bacterial pathogens within hours, rather than days [66]. However, these tools are still in the experimental phase and require further validation before they can be widely implemented in clinical settings. De-

veloping cost-effective, user-friendly diagnostic devices that can be deployed in both high-income and low-income settings remains a significant challenge for the global AMR response.

Public Engagement and Education

Public perception and behavior significantly influence the success of AMR interventions. Misunderstanding the role of antibiotics, coupled with a lack of awareness about the dangers of AMR, has contributed to the overuse and misuse of these medications. Public education campaigns are therefore crucial in changing behavior, promoting responsible antimicrobial use, and reducing the spread of resistant infections [67] attitudes, and perceptions (KAP.

Bridging the Gap between High- and Low-Income Countries

AMR disproportionately affects LMICs, where healthcare systems are often under-resourced, and regulations on antibiotic use are weaker. The burden of resistant infections in LMICs is compounded by poor sanitation, overcrowding, and limited access to diagnostic tools and second-line antibiotics. Bridging the gap between high-income countries (HICs) and LMICs is critical for global AMR control, as resistant bacteria do not respect national borders [68].

High-income countries (HICs) generally benefit from well-resourced healthcare systems that include advanced diagnostics, ample healthcare providers, and robust access to second-line treatments. These elements support more effective AMR management through timely detection and treatment of resistant infections.

Conversely, LMICs face numerous systemic challenges. For instance, limited access to essential diagnostic tools and trained healthcare professionals impedes accurate and timely identification of resistant pathogens. Furthermore, LMICs often struggle with resource constraints that make it difficult to implement effective infection control measures in healthcare settings. The availability of critical infrastructure, such as intensive care units, specialized facilities, and essential medical supplies, is also far more limited compared to HICs. Rural areas in particular are disproportionately affected, with patients frequently needing to travel long distances to reach healthcare facilities, reducing access to timely medical care.

Conclusion

While the One Health approach offers a promising framework for tackling the global AMR crisis, its large-scale implementation faces significant barriers, particularly in LMICs. Challenges such as resource limitations, weak regulatory frameworks, and restricted access to diagnostics and treatments hinder the effectiveness of AMR interventions. Coordination across human, animal, and environmental health sectors remains difficult, as LMICs often lack the infrastructure and funding needed to sustain integrated efforts. Addressing these barriers is crucial to ensure the One Health approach is not only a concept but an actionable strategy.

Recommendations

- 1. Strengthen International Collaboration:** Establish partnerships between high-income countries and LMICs to share expertise, technology, and resources, ensuring that LMICs receive the support needed to build sustainable AMR interventions.
 - 2. Increase Funding for Capacity Building:** Allocate international funding to train healthcare workers, veterinarians, and environmental specialists in LMICs, enhancing their ability to detect, prevent, and manage AMR through coordinated efforts.
 - 3. Develop Context-Specific Regulatory Frameworks:** Support LMICs in crafting regulatory policies that are tailored to their specific contexts, including monitoring and regulating the use of antimicrobials in human medicine, agriculture, and environmental management.
 - 4. Invest in Diagnostic Infrastructure:** Expand access to rapid and affordable diagnostic tools in LMICs to enable timely identification of resistant infections, reducing the misuse of antibiotics.
 - 5. Promote Public Awareness Campaigns:** Launch education initiatives aimed at improving public understanding of AMR and the importance of responsible antimicrobial use, focusing on high-risk regions and populations.
- By addressing these challenges with targeted and practical solutions, the One Health approach can be more effectively applied to control AMR globally.

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Competing interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicting interests related to this research. All findings and conclusions presented in this study are based solely on the data collected and the analyses performed, without any influence from external parties or financial interests. The research was conducted with the utmost integrity and objectivity to ensure unbiased results.

Informed consent statement

Not applicable.

Statement of ethics

Was in accordance with ethical guidelines.

Authors' Contributions

JGM, KM, and AO all participated in literature review and writing final manuscript. JGM designed the graphical introduction figure.

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